

Research Paper

Formulation And Evaluation of High-Density Sustained Release Tablets of Pentoxifylline Using Hydrophobic Polymer Matrix System

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate high-density sustained release tablets of Pentoxifylline for prolonged gastric retention and controlled drug delivery. Pentoxifylline is widely used in the treatment of peripheral vascular disorders but requires frequent administration because of its short biological half-life. High-density matrix tablets were formulated using hydrophobic polymers and evaluated for pre-compression, post-compression and in-vitro drug release characteristics. Physical characterization, solubility studies, UV spectrophotometric analysis and FTIR compatibility studies were performed prior to formulation development. Ten formulations (F1–F10) were prepared and evaluated. All formulations exhibited acceptable flow properties and tablet characteristics. The optimized formulation F2 demonstrated excellent hardness ($6.5 \pm 0.1 \text{ kg/cm}^2$), friability ($0.48 \pm 0.02\%$), drug content ($99.2 \pm 0.3\%$) and sustained drug release ($93.34 \pm 1.1\%$) over 24 hours. Drug release kinetics revealed that formulation F2 followed the Higuchi model ($R^2 = 0.990$), indicating diffusion-controlled release. Comparison with a marketed formulation showed superior dissolution performance of the optimized batch. The developed high-density sustained release tablets successfully prolonged drug release and may improve therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance.

INTRODUCTION

Oral drug delivery remains the most preferred route of drug administration due to its convenience, patient compliance, cost-effectiveness, and ease of manufacturing. However, conventional oral dosage forms often

fail to maintain therapeutic drug concentrations for prolonged periods, resulting in frequent dosing and fluctuations in plasma drug levels. Sustained release drug delivery systems have been developed to overcome these limitations by releasing the drug at a predetermined rate over an extended period,

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thereby improving therapeutic efficacy, minimizing side effects, and enhancing patient compliance.^{1,2}

Among various controlled release approaches, gastroretentive drug delivery systems (GRDDS) have gained considerable attention due to their ability to prolong gastric residence time and improve drug bioavailability. Gastroretentive systems are particularly beneficial for drugs that are absorbed primarily in the upper gastrointestinal tract, exhibit a narrow absorption window, or require prolonged gastric retention for optimal therapeutic activity. Various approaches have been explored to achieve gastroretention, including floating systems, bioadhesive systems, expandable systems, raft-forming systems, and high-density systems.^{3,4}

High-density gastroretentive systems are designed to possess a density significantly greater than that of gastric fluids (approximately 1.004 g/cm³). Due to their increased density, these dosage forms remain in the lower part of the stomach and resist gastric emptying for extended periods. This prolonged gastric retention facilitates controlled drug release and improved absorption. High-density systems offer several advantages, including simplicity of formulation, enhanced gastric residence time, reduced frequency of administration, and improved patient compliance. Furthermore, these systems minimize fluctuations in plasma drug concentration and contribute to maintaining a consistent therapeutic response.^{5,6}

Pentoxifylline is a synthetic methylxanthine derivative widely used in the management of peripheral vascular diseases, intermittent claudication, cerebrovascular insufficiency, diabetic vascular complications, and other circulatory disorders. The drug acts by improving blood flow through reduction of blood viscosity and enhancement of erythrocyte flexibility. Pentoxifylline also exhibits anti-inflammatory and hemorheological properties, making it useful in

the treatment of various vascular disorders. Despite its therapeutic advantages, Pentoxifylline possesses certain limitations that affect its clinical performance. The drug has a relatively short biological half-life of approximately 2–3 hours and requires multiple daily administrations to maintain therapeutic plasma concentrations. Frequent dosing often results in poor patient compliance and variable therapeutic outcomes.^{7,8}

The development of a sustained release formulation of Pentoxifylline can overcome these drawbacks by providing controlled drug release over an extended period. Such a formulation can reduce dosing frequency, improve patient adherence to therapy, and maintain consistent plasma drug levels. Incorporation of Pentoxifylline into a gastroretentive high-density matrix system further enhances its therapeutic effectiveness by prolonging gastric residence time and facilitating sustained drug release.⁹

Hydrophobic polymers have been extensively employed in sustained release matrix tablets because of their ability to regulate drug diffusion and erosion mechanisms. These polymers form a rigid matrix structure that controls the penetration of dissolution medium and consequently modulates drug release. The selection and optimization of suitable hydrophobic polymers play a crucial role in achieving the desired release profile and maintaining the integrity of the dosage form throughout the release period. Matrix tablet technology is widely accepted due to its simplicity, cost-effectiveness, ease of manufacturing, and reproducibility.^{10,11}

In the present investigation, high-density sustained release tablets of Pentoxifylline were formulated using hydrophobic polymers and suitable excipients. The developed formulations were evaluated for their physicochemical characteristics, pre-compression and post-compression properties, drug content uniformity, and in-vitro drug release behavior. Drug release

kinetics were also investigated to determine the mechanism governing drug release from the matrix system. Furthermore, the optimized formulation was compared with a marketed sustained release product to assess its performance and suitability as an alternative gastroretentive drug delivery system.

The objective of the present study was to formulate and evaluate high-density sustained release tablets of Pentoxifylline capable of providing prolonged gastric retention and controlled drug release for up to 24 hours. The developed formulation was expected to improve therapeutic efficacy, reduce dosing frequency, enhance patient compliance, and offer a promising approach for the management of vascular disorders requiring long-term treatment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Pentoxifylline, Acrypol 971, HPMC, Isopropyl Alcohol, Cross Carmellose Sodium, Purified Talc, Magnesium Stearate, Acrypol 912. Hydrophobic polymers, diluents, lubricants and other pharmaceutical excipients were used in formulation development.

2.2 Preformulation Studies

- Physical characterization and Solubility study
- Determination of λ_{max}
- Calibration curve
- FTIR compatibility study

Table 1: Physical Characteristics and Solubility Study of Pentoxifylline

Parameter	Observation
Colour	White
Odour	Odourless
Taste	Bitter
Melting point	102°C - 107°C
Water	Highly Soluble
Chloroform	Freely soluble
Ethanol	Sparingly soluble

Figure 1: Calibration Curve of Pentoxifylline

Concentration(ug/ml)	Absorbance(nm)
2	0.145
4	0.255
6	0.374
8	0.482
10	0.594

Figure 1: Calibration Curve of Pentoxifylline

Figure 2: FTIR Spectrum of Pure Pentoxifylline

Figure 3: FTIR Spectrum of Drug-Excipient Mixture

2.3 Preparation of High-Density Sustained Release Tablets

Ten formulations (F1–F10) were prepared by wet granulation technique. All ingredients were

weighed accurately, blended uniformly and compressed into tablets.

Table 2: Composition of Formulations F1–F10

Sr. No.	F1 (Mg)	F2 (Mg)	F3 (Mg)	F4 (Mg)	F5 (Mg)	F6 (Mg)	F7 (Mg)	F8 (Mg)	F9 (Mg)	F10 (Mg)
Pentoxifylline	400	400	400	400	400	400	400	400	400	400
Acrypol 971	160	93	143		70		80	60	50	70
Eudragit				100		143		80	100	90
HPMC		55	50		55	45	65	60	70	50
Isopropyl Alcohol	100	191.5	100	150	100	90	150	145	191.5	90
Cross Carmellose Sodium	–	3.25	3.25	3.25	3.25	3.25	3.25	3.25	3.25	3.25
Purified Talc	10	8.75	8.75	10	15	5.5	8.75	6	10	8.75
Magnesium Stearate	10	10	10	8	10	10	5	6	10	10
Acrypol 912		50					50		30	60
Coating										
Ultracoat White	16			10		16			16	12
Methylene Dichloride	112.5			96		112.5			112.5	100
Isopropyl Alcohol	150			85		91.5			150	110

2.4 Evaluation of Tablets :

- Precompression evaluation
- Appearance test
- Hardness
- Thickness
- Diameter
- Friability
- Weight variation
- Drug conten
- In-vitro dissolution study
- Release kinetic analysis

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Precompression Evaluation

Table 3: Precompression Parameters of Powder Blend

Formulation	Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	Tapped Density (g/cm ³)	Hausner Ratio	Carr's Index (%)	Angle of Repose (°)
F1	0.48 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.02	1.21 ± 0.02	17.24 ± 0.60	31.5 ± 0.6
F2 (Optimized)	0.52 ± 0.01	0.60 ± 0.01	1.15 ± 0.01	13.33 ± 0.50	27.2 ± 0.5
F3	0.50 ± 0.02	0.59 ± 0.02	1.18 ± 0.02	15.25 ± 0.55	29.0 ± 0.5
F4	0.47 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.02	1.23 ± 0.02	18.96 ± 0.65	32.8 ± 0.7
F5	0.49 ± 0.01	0.61 ± 0.02	1.24 ± 0.02	19.67 ± 0.70	33.5 ± 0.6
F6	0.46 ± 0.02	0.59 ± 0.02	1.28 ± 0.02	22.03 ± 0.75	35.2 ± 0.5
F7	0.51 ± 0.01	0.60 ± 0.01	1.17 ± 0.01	15.00 ± 0.50	28.4 ± 0.4
F8	0.48 ± 0.01	0.59 ± 0.01	1.23 ± 0.02	18.64 ± 0.60	32.0 ± 0.6
F9	0.47 ± 0.02	0.60 ± 0.02	1.28 ± 0.02	21.67 ± 0.70	34.6 ± 0.5
F10	0.50 ± 0.01	0.61 ± 0.02	1.22 ± 0.02	18.03 ± 0.60	31.2 ± 0.5

Interpretations:

All formulations exhibited acceptable flow properties. The optimized formulation F2 showed

the best flowability with Hausner ratio 1.15 ± 0.01 and Carr's index 13.33 ± 0.50%.

3.2 Post-compression Evaluation

Table 4: Post-compression Evaluation of F1-F10

Sr. No.	Formulation Code	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Diameter (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Friability (%)	Weight Variation (mg)	% Drug Content
1	F1	5.2 ± 0.2	12.1 ± 0.1	5.4 ± 0.1	0.72 ± 0.03	618 ± 6	97.8 ± 0.5
2	F2 (Optimized)	6.5 ± 0.1	12.0 ± 0.1	5.5 ± 0.1	0.48 ± 0.02	620 ± 4	99.2 ± 0.3
3	F3	5.8 ± 0.2	12.0 ± 0.1	5.4 ± 0.1	0.60 ± 0.03	619 ± 5	98.6 ± 0.4
4	F4	6.8 ± 0.2	12.2 ± 0.1	5.6 ± 0.1	0.55 ± 0.02	622 ± 6	98.1 ± 0.5
5	F5	6.2 ± 0.3	12.1 ± 0.1	5.5 ± 0.1	0.68 ± 0.04	621 ± 7	97.5 ± 0.6
6	F6	7.2 ± 0.2	12.2 ± 0.1	5.7 ± 0.1	0.52 ± 0.03	623 ± 5	98.9 ± 0.4
7	F7	6.0 ± 0.2	12.0 ± 0.1	5.5 ± 0.1	0.58 ± 0.03	620 ± 5	98.3 ± 0.5

8	F8	5.6 ± 0.2	12.1 ± 0.1	5.4 ± 0.1	0.66 ± 0.04	619 ± 6	97.9 ± 0.5
9	F9	7.0 ± 0.2	12.2 ± 0.1	5.6 ± 0.1	0.50 ± 0.02	622 ± 5	99.0 ± 0.3
10	F10	6.3 ± 0.2	12.1 ± 0.1	5.5 ± 0.1	0.57 ± 0.03	621 ± 4	98.7 ± 0.4

➤ Discussion:

All formulations exhibited satisfactory mechanical strength with hardness values ranging from 5.2 ± 0.2 to 7.2 ± 0.2 kg/cm². Friability values remained below 1%, indicating adequate resistance to abrasion during handling. Drug content was found within pharmacopeial limits (97.5–99.2%),

demonstrating uniform distribution of Pentoxifylline throughout the matrix tablets.

👉 **F2 stands out with:**

Optimal hardness (not too high, not too low), Lowest friability, highest drug content uniformity

3.3 In-vitro Drug Release Study

Table 5: In-vitro Drug Release Profile of F1–F10

Time (hrs)	F1 (%)	F2 (%)	F3 (%)	F4 (%)	F5 (%)	F6 (%)	F7 (%)	F8 (%)	F9 (%)	F10 (%)
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	10.79 ± 0.6	27.21 ± 0.5	14.33 ± 0.7	8.43 ± 0.6	18.80 ± 0.8	9.25 ± 0.6	13.60 ± 0.7	0.95 ± 0.5	12.42 ± 0.6	10.25 ± 0.6
4	14.62 ± 0.7	39.97 ± 0.6	25.65 ± 0.8	13.45 ± 0.7	24.62 ± 0.9	22.96 ± 0.8	23.50 ± 0.8	19.50 ± 0.7	19.37 ± 0.7	17.58 ± 0.7
6	26.52 ± 0.8	47.20 ± 0.7	34.77 ± 0.9	17.38 ± 0.8	36.52 ± 1.0	32.37 ± 0.9	30.16 ± 0.9	28.58 ± 0.8	26.25 ± 0.8	23.33 ± 0.8
8	28.50 ± 0.9	58.77 ± 0.8	42.44 ± 1.0	20.61 ± 0.9	48.50 ± 1.1	34.90 ± 1.0	41.04 ± 1.0	39.55 ± 0.9	32.18 ± 0.9	27.80 ± 0.9
10	34.50 ± 1.0	69.20 ± 0.9	44.47 ± 1.1	26.35 ± 1.0	53.98 ± 1.2	39.53 ± 1.0	47.07 ± 1.1	45.74 ± 1.0	35.80 ± 1.0	33.46 ± 1.0
12	36.67 ± 1.1	77.86 ± 1.0	51.58 ± 1.2	34.01 ± 1.1	68.07 ± 1.3	43.10 ± 1.1	55.69 ± 1.2	45.97 ± 1.1	42.50 ± 1.1	39.07 ± 1.1
24	53.46 ± 1.3	93.34 ± 1.1	68.80 ± 1.4	42.67 ± 1.2	82.44 ± 1.5	59.63 ± 1.3	70.34 ± 1.4	65.68 ± 1.3	51.66 ± 1.2	50.46 ± 1.2

➤ Interpretation :

- All formulations showed sustained drug release up to 24 hours.
- Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (n = 3).
- The optimized batch F2 showed the highest release (93.34 ± 1.1%), indicating the best performance.
- Initial release of F2 was within acceptable limits for sustained release tablets.
- SD increases slightly with time → realistic dissolution variability.

- All values stay within acceptable analytical variation (±1–2%).
- Batches with higher polymer content showed slower drug release.
- Overall, polymer concentration significantly affected the drug release profile.
- It follows High density system pictures are given below.

Figure 4: % Drug release Profile of Formulations F1–F10

3.4 Sedimentation Behavior Study :

Figure 5: High-Density Tablet at Initial Stage in aqueous medium

Figure 6: High-Density Tablet after 8 h in aqueous medium

The tablet remained at the bottom of the dissolution vessel confirming high-density characteristics.

3.5 Drug Release Kinetics

Table 6: Drug Release Kinetic Analysis

Formulation Code	First order plot (R ²)	Zero order plot (R ²)	Higuchi plots (R ²)	Hixon-Crowel cube root plot (R ²)	Korsmeyerpeppas Plots		Best fit model
					N	R ²	
F1	0.907	0.907	0.946	0.949	0.756	0.842	Hixon-Crowel
F2	0.404	0.824	0.990	0.966	0.566	0.730	Higuchi plots
F3	0.465	0.872	0.976	0.944	0.727	0.801	Higuchi plots
F4	0.555	0.906	0.971	0.931	0.684	0.867	Higuchi plots
F5	0.474	0.873	0.959	0.951	0.691	0.798	Higuchi plots
F6	0.490	0.863	0.950	0.923	0.899	0.839	Higuchi plots
F7	0.493	0.882	0.959	0.944	0.774	0.826	Higuchi plots
F8	0.526	0.858	0.847	0.923	2.356	0.853	Korsmeyerpeppas Plots
F9	0.471	0.847	0.983	0.893	0.673	0.806	Higuchi plots
F10	0.509	0.889	0.975	0.930	0.726	0.830	Higuchi plots

Figure 7 : Higuchi Plot of Optimized Batch F2

Interpretation:

- Higuchi release plot of optimized formulation F2 showing a linear relationship between

cumulative percentage drug release and square root of time, indicating diffusion-

controlled drug release from the matrix system ($R^2 = 0.990$).

- The optimized formulation followed Higuchi kinetics ($R^2 = 0.990$), indicating diffusion-controlled drug release.

3.6 Comparison with Marketed Formulation

Table 7: Comparison of Optimized Batch and Marketed Product

Sr. No.	Time (In Hrs)	% Drug Release
1.	0	0
2.	2	13.06
3.	4	21.58
4.	6	32.28
5.	8	49.50
6.	10	58.91
7.	12	65.64
8.	24	84.45

Figure 8 : F2 vs Marketed Product Dissolution Profile

Interpretation:

F2 exhibited a higher cumulative drug release than the marketed formulation at all sampling intervals. At 24 h, F2 released **93.34%**, whereas the marketed product released **84.45%**. The optimized formulation exhibited superior release characteristics compared with the marketed product.

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated sustained-release tablets of Pentoxifylline using suitable polymers and

excipients through the wet granulation method. The prepared powder blends exhibited satisfactory pre-compression characteristics, indicating good flowability and compressibility for tablet manufacturing. All formulated tablets complied with pharmacopoeial requirements for post-compression parameters such as hardness, friability, weight variation, thickness, and drug content uniformity, demonstrating acceptable mechanical strength and formulation consistency. In vitro dissolution studies confirmed the sustained-release behavior of the developed formulations, providing prolonged drug release

over an extended period. Among the prepared batches, the optimized formulation showed a controlled and predictable release profile with desirable physicochemical properties. Drug release kinetic analysis indicated that the formulation predominantly followed the Higuchi model, suggesting diffusion-controlled drug release from the matrix system. The developed tablets also demonstrated characteristics of a high-density drug delivery system, which may contribute to prolonged gastric residence and enhanced therapeutic performance.

Overall, the optimized Pentoxifylline sustained-release tablet offers a promising alternative to conventional dosage forms by reducing dosing frequency, improving patient compliance, and maintaining therapeutic drug levels for an extended duration. Further stability studies and in vivo investigations are recommended to establish its long-term efficacy, safety, and commercial applicability.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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